

From Missionary Records to Data Narratives: Reconstructing the Histories of Tamil Religious Objects (1706-1741)

Maria Ionita, Università di Bologna
maria.monica.ionita.ro@gmail.com

In 1670, the Danish crown granted a 40-year charter to a second Danish East India Company. Among the conditions outlined in the charter was a clear emphasis on converting the local population to Christianity (Fenger, 1863, p. 13). For this purpose, missionaries from the Danish-Halle Mission were sent over to South India. Economically dependent on the Danish fort and European donations (Hudson, 2020, p. 26), the mission operated as a structural extension of colonial power, its work entangled with colonial objectives and serving as a theological justification for European presence (Pranger, 2023, p. 141). Within this context, Indian religious artefacts began to be sent to Europe by Christian missionaries. These objects demonstrated the mission's success, served as trophies over what was described as idolatry, and helped secure support from the Danish crown (Etter, 2019, p.192; Zaunstöck, 2020, p. 224). This study examines how digital methods can reconstruct the colonial-era movement of Tamil religious artefacts from South India to European museums, focusing on the Christian missionary activities of the Danish-Halle Mission between 1706 and 1741 in Tranquebar. Instead of relying on pre-existing datasets, it builds a dataset from scratch using missionary journals, letters, and the 1741 Halle Cabinet inventory. The entire process - data gathering, cleaning, modelling, and interpretation - is approached as a form of digital storytelling, demonstrating how new narratives are revealed through the computational structuring and analysis of archival evidence.

Reconstructing the history of displaced artefacts from this period is methodologically complex. Documentation from the Danish East India Company is fragmentary, especially before 1732, due to major archival losses (Felbæk, 1990, p. 106). Moreover, only a few artefacts appear in official records, while many remain hidden within archival silences created by smuggling and unrecorded missionary collecting. Religious objects circulated through informal networks and are absent from auction account books and import-export surveys. Smuggled items never appear in trade documents (Martens, 2017, p. 11). Yet the existence of this practice is proved by the collections of European

museums, particularly in Denmark and Halle, which hold large numbers of Tamil religious artefacts. Missionary correspondence also confirms this parallel economy: in 1710, Bartholomäus Ziegenbalg, a key figure of the mission, warned new recruits not to become “half-merchants” seeking “rarities in the Heathen World or to purchase a few uncertain riches” (Ziegenbalg et al., 1718, Part II, Letter VII, p. 49). These traces point to a rich but fragmented narrative landscape that digital methods are well-positioned to uncover.

The research responds to a recognised gap: although digitally-assisted provenance investigation is expanding, digital tools are rarely applied to object biographies and large-scale analysis (Dunn et al., 2019, p. 8; Rother et al., 2023, p. 122). Further, it is recognised that structured data maps can reveal “points of historical tangency” and highlight blind spots (Luzan, 2023, p. 100). Attempts to document the biographies of Indian religious artefacts are not new. Most notably, *Lives of Indian Images* (1999) by Richard H. Davis applies a biographical framework to such objects. While Davis offers exemplary case studies and addresses processes of colonial acquisition, his analysis is largely confined to British colonial contexts and a case study scale. Building on this foundation, the present research constructs an extensive dataset to identify broader patterns of artefact acquisition and to examine the relationships between Protestant missionaries and Tamil communities. The central research question is: How can the process of constructing a digital corpus and conducting computational analysis reveal narrative points otherwise hidden within the colonial collecting practices of the Danish-Halle Mission (1706-1741)?

The project draws on two main primary sources: (1) missionary journals and letters from Tranquebar and (2) the 1741 Halle Cabinet inventory. Together, they contain scattered references to the acquisition, transformation, surrender, and circulation of Hindu objects. Methodologically, this research combines two complementary approaches. The first is the construction of object biographies in the sense developed by Igor Kopytoff (1988), centred on a case study of religious objects surrendered by a Tamil family during their conversion to Christianity in the first half of the 18th century. Dispersed textual references are structured into a dataset of all objects that are noted to have been in the possession of the Danish-Halle Mission’s Cabinet of Curiosities in Halle, Germany, in 1741, which will be published as supplementary material. This leads to the second approach, which is computational analysis that maps patterns of transfer, including type of procurement, correlations between material types, and categories of objects transported, whether ritual objects, instruments, sculptures, or other artefacts.

The object biography traces the micro-level narrative of specific artefacts and the circumstances of their displacement, while the structured analysis reveals macro-level patterns across the corpus. Due to the fragmentary nature of the sources, object biographies will always be partial reconstructions. The structured analysis does not eliminate this limitation but mitigates it by revealing patterns across the corpus that remain inaccessible to individual case studies. The project demonstrates how digital methods, when combined with object biography approaches, can uncover narrative dimensions obscured within fragmented colonial archives. More broadly, it argues that computational approaches remain underutilised in provenance research, despite their particular relevance for objects entangled in histories of colonial displacement.

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